

Clinico-Hematological Profile of Multiple Myeloma Patients in a Tertiary Care Hospital - A 1 Year Study**Brahmjeet¹, Deepak Maini², Sunita Kulhari³, Guman Singh⁴**¹Resident 3rd Year, Department of Pathology, SPMC, Bikaner (Raj.)²Resident 3rd Year, Department of Pathology, SPMC, Bikaner (Raj.)³Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, SPMC, Bikaner (Raj.)⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Radiotherapy, SPMC, Bikaner (Raj.)

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Multiple myeloma is a clonal malignant neoplasm of plasma cells originating in the bone marrow along with the presence of monoclonal immunoglobulin in the blood and/or urine associated with end-organ damage.**Methods:** The present study was done prospectively in 52 patients of multiple myeloma diagnosed over a period of 1 years from 01 January 2023 to 31 Dec 2023 in our teaching hospital. All newly diagnosed patients of Multiple Myeloma with relevant data during the above mentioned period were collected from the records and included in the study.**Results:** Generalised weakness was the most common presenting complaint seen in 84.61% patients followed by bone pain in 76.92%. Hematological features were anemia in 38 patients(73%), total leucocyte count(TLC) was raised in 5 patients (10%), pancytopenia was seen in 01 patient(1.9%), Erythrocyte sedimentation rate(ESR) was raised in 37 patients(71.1 %), Rouleaux formation was observed in 31 patients (59.6 %).**Conclusion:** In our study, generalized weakness is the most common clinical presentation followed by bone pain. Anemia is the most common hematological manifestation.**Keywords:** Multiple myeloma, Pain, Weakness.

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Introduction

Multiple myeloma is a clonal malignant neoplasm of plasma cells originating in the bone marrow along with the presence of monoclonal immunoglobulin in the blood and/or urine associated with end-organ damage.

It accounts for 1% of all malignant tumors, 10 - 15% of all hematologic malignancies and 20% of deaths from hematological malignancies

Multiple myeloma is a disease of the elderly with a peak age of 60-70 years at presentation.

It is more common in males when compared to females.

Etiology of the disease is largely unknown various factors like environmental, occupational, radiation exposure, metal industries, benzene exposure and preexisting medical conditions have been found to increase the incidence of Multiple myeloma[1].

Aims & Objectives:

1. Identify initial basic laboratory features of multiple myeloma (MM)

2. Assess the biochemical, hematological profile and electrophoretic pattern consistent with clinical symptoms of multiple myeloma(MM)

3. Aid physicians to entertain a high index of suspicion and therefore target their investigations in order to prevent late presentation and avert complications.

Material & Method

The present study was done prospectively in 52 patients of multiple myeloma diagnosed over a period of 1 years from 01 January 2023 to 31 Dec 2023 in our teaching hospital. All newly diagnosed patients of Multiple Myeloma with relevant data during the above mentioned period were collected from the records and included in the study.

For evaluation of each case, Revised International Myeloma Working Group criteria was applied.. As per the revised International Myeloma Working Group criteria, the diagnosis of multiple myeloma requires the presence of one or more myeloma defining events (MDE) in addition to evidence of 10% or more clonal plasma cells on bone marrow examination or biopsy-proven plasmacytoma.MDE

consist of established CRAB features (hypercalcemia, renal failure, anemia, or lytic bone lesions) as well as three specific biomarkers- clonal bone marrow plasma cells $\geq 60\%$, Serum involved / uninvolved free light chain ratio ≥ 100 (provided the absolute level of the involved light chain is at least 100mg/L) and more than one focal lesion(5mm or greater in size) on magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).[3]

Exclusion Criteria: (1) Old diagnosed cases of multiple myeloma that are under treatment. (2) Treatment part of multiple myeloma.

Observations

Out of 52 patients, 37 (71%) were men and 15 (29%) were women. The male to female ratio was 2.4:1. Sixth decade was the most common age group in our study and only 3(5.7%) patients were younger than 40 years. The mean age of patient in our study population was 59 year as shown in the table.

Table - 1. Age wise distribution

Age	Male	Female	Total
<40yr	3	0	3
41-50yr	8	2	10
51-60yr	8	7	15
61-70yr	13	4	17
>70yr	5	2	7
Total	37	15	52

Generalised weakness was the most common presenting complaint seen in 84.61% patients followed by bone pain in 76.92% as shown in the table below:

Hematological features were anemia in 38 patients (73%), total leucocyte count(TLC) was raised in 5

patients (10 %), pancytopenia was seen in 01 patient (1.9%), Erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) was raised in 37 patients (71.1 %), Rouleaux formation was observed in 31 patients (59.6 %).

Table no- 1. Clinic-hematological manifestation

Clinico-hematological manifestations	No. of cases
Anaemia	38
Fever	23
Bone pain	40
Generalised weakness	44
Renal impairment	16
Pathological fracture	02
Motor weakness in lower limb	01

Serum creatinine was raised in 12 patients (23.07 %), serum calcium was raised in 36% of patients, serum protein electrophoresis shows M band in gamma region in 91.30% of patients. Urine bence-jones proteins was found positive in 30.76 % as shown in table.

Table 3. Investigations

Investigations	Result	Percentage %
ESR	Elevated(>30mm/hr)	71.10
PBF	Rouleaux formation	59.60
Sr. Creatinine	>2mg/dl	23.07
Sr. Electrophoresis	M band in gamma region	91.30
Urine Bence-jones proteins	Positive	30.76
TLC	Raised	10
Serum calcium	>12mg/dl	36

Among skeletal involvement, 35 patients had osteolytic lesions (67%) on radiological investigations. Spine was the most frequent site of involvement (62.86%) followed by ribs and pelvis(28.57%) and skull(8.57%), as shown in Table.

Table 4: Osteolytic lesions

Osteolytic lesions	No. of patients	%
Spine	22	62.86
Ribs & pelvis	10	28.57
Skull	3	8.57

On bone marrow examination, more than 70% of plasma cells in 01 patients (1.92%), 4 patient (7.69 %) had 51-70% of plasma cells, 20 patients (38.46%) had plasma cells in the range of 31-50%, 16 patients (30.77 %) had plasma cells in the range of 20-30% and 11 patients (21.16%) had plasma cells in the range of 10-19% as shown in Table below.

Table 5: Plasma cells

% of plasma cells	No. of patients	% of patients
10-19%	11	21.16
20-30%	16	30.77
31-50%	20	38.46
51-70%	04	7.69
>70%	01	1.92
Total	52	100

Rouleaux Formation in Peripheral Blood Film

DUTCHER BODIES

FLAME CELL

Multinucleated plasma cell

Binucleate plasma cell

Bone marrow aspiration smear characteristically showed a high percentage of plasma cells with binucleation, Flame cell, Russell bodies and Dutcher bodies as shown in the figure:-

Discussion

The age group included in our study ranged from 34-82 years, with a mean age of 59 years. The commonest age group at presentation was the 6th decade, which is similar to studies done [2,3,4,5].

The majority of the patients in our study were males with a M:F ratio of 2.4:1 which is similar to some Studies [6,7].

The most common clinical manifestation at the time of presentation was generalised weakness (84.61%), followed by bone pains (76.92%) in this study. These findings are in concordance with other studies [8,9]. The majority of the patients were anemic (73%) this finding is comparable to other studies [3,8].

Rouleaux formation was seen in (59.60%) patients in the present study. This finding was consistent with the study of Sheik et al. [3] (57%), Aditi Gupta et al. [2] (58%) while Kaur P et al. [11] have reported rouleaux formation on peripheral smear exam in (82%) of cases

Osteolytic lesions are most commonly seen in spine (62.86%) which is similar to the study conducted by Sheik et al.³(63%)

Hypercalcemia was found in 36% of patients in our study, which is comparable to the studies done by Aditi Gupta et al. [2] (37.14%), Sheik et al [3] (32%), Parwaiz A, et al [8] (31.4%).

23.07% of the patients had elevated serum creatinine, which is consistent with the findings in the studies of Parwaiz A, et al [8] (24.6%) and Ramani P.N et al⁹(30%), Kaushik et al. [1] (16%) and Kyle RA et al. [10] (19%) which is in contrast

to study conducted by Aditi Gupta et al. [2] (58.57%).

An M-band on serum electrophoresis was detected in 91.30% in this study which is similar to the other studies conducted by Kaur P et al. [11] (92.8%) and Aditi Gupta et al.²(97%).

Urine bence jones protein was positive in 16 patients (30.76%) which is similar to studies conducted by Sheik et al. [3] (27%) and Diwan AG et al. [4] (30%).

Conclusion

Multiple myeloma is a disease that affects multiple organ systems and has a diverse clinical presentation.

Multiple myeloma is mainly seen in people over the age of 60 years.

In our study, generalized weakness is the most common clinical presentation followed by bone pain. Anemia is the most common hematological manifestation.

When an elderly patient presents with varied clinical manifestations such as infections, pathological fracture, Generalised weakness, back pain, renal impairment, and unexplained anemia, Multiple myeloma should be investigated as a differential diagnosis.

References:-

1. Kaushik R, Thakur RK, Gulati A, Sharma SK. Multiple myeloma: clinico-hematological profile in a tertiary care hospital: a three years study. *Annals of Pathology and Laboratory Medicine*. 2017 Oct 25;4(5):270-5.
2. Gupta A, Malukani K, Dhamnani G, Tripapathi S, Wankhade S, Raghuwanshi A. Clinico-pathological Profile of Patients with Multiple Myeloma: An Ambispective Study. *Journal of*

- Clinical and Diagnostic Research. 2023 Feb 1;17(2):EC46-52.
3. Sheik N, Krupal Variganji S, Renuka Inuganti V, Uppala P, Meghana Bolla P. Clinico-hematological profile of multiple myeloma in a teaching hospital - A 2 year study. Arch Cytol Histopathol Res 2019;4(4):305-309.
 4. Diwan AG, Gandhi SA, Krishna K, Shinde VP. Clinical profile of the spectrum of multiple myeloma in a teaching hospital. Med J Dr DY Patil Univ. 2014;7(2):185-188.
 5. Ramani PN, Sreeraj V, Binub K. Clinical profile of multiple myeloma in a tertiary medical college northern Kerala, India. Int J Med Paediatr Oncol 2019;5(2):58-61.
 6. Kalita LK, Kalita C, Gogoi PK, et al. A clinico-epidemiological study of multiple myeloma – A hospital based study at Gauhati Medical College & Hospital, Guwahati, Assam. J. Evid. Based Med. Healthc. 2016; 3(36), 1788-1794. DOI: 10.18410/jebmh/2016/400
 7. Parwaiz A, et al. Clinicopathological Spectrum of Multiple Myeloma: Experience of an Institute in Eastern India. Haematol Int J 2023, 7 (2):00220.
 8. Chowdhury, Md. (2018). A Clinical and Laboratory Profile of Multiple Myeloma. Journal of Enam Medical College. 8.159.10.3329/jemc.v8i3.38366
 9. P.n R, Sreeraj V, Binub K, Clinical profile of multiple myeloma in a tertiary medical college northern Kerala, India. IP Int J Med Paediatr Oncol 2019;5(2):58-61
 10. Kyle RA, Gertz MA, Witzig TE, Lust JA, Lacy MQ, Dispenzieri A, Fonseca R, Rajkumar SV, Offord JR, Larson DR, Plevak ME, Therneau TM, Greipp PR. Review of 1027 patients with newly diagnosed multiple myeloma. Mayo Clin Proc. 2003 Jan;78(1):21-33. doi: 10.4065/78.1.21. PMID: 12528874.
 11. Kaur P, Shah BS, Bajaj P. Multiple myeloma: A clinical and pathological profile. GJO. 2014; 16:14-20